

A static representation of quantum circuits without causality or preferred direction of time

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Abstract

We propose a new representation of quantum circuits that eliminates the projection steps traditionally associated with measurement, resulting in a fundamentally static depiction of the circuit without intrinsic time ordering. In this framework, the evolution of the quantum system is fully unitary and deterministic, with no irreversible processes. By decoupling physical evolution from subjective measurement outcomes, this approach offers a novel, time-symmetric view of quantum mechanics, free from traditional notions of causality and the directional flow of time.

1 Measurement = Entanglement + Projection

Consider an observer, O , represented by a Hilbert space H_O , initially in the state $|0\rangle_O \in H_O$ at a given time t_a . This observer performs a measurement on a system S , represented by a Hilbert space H_S and initially in a state $|\phi\rangle_S \in H_S$ at t_a .

According to quantum mechanics [1], a Measurement consists of two distinct steps:

Entanglement A physical interaction between O and S , in which the combined system $O + S$ evolves unitarily into an entangled state $|\Psi\rangle \in H_O \otimes H_S$.

$$|0\rangle_O \otimes |\phi\rangle_S \text{ at } t_a \mapsto |\Psi\rangle \in H_O \otimes H_S \text{ at } t_b \quad (1)$$

Projection An orthonormal basis $\{|e_i\rangle_O\}_i$ for H_O is assigned to the Projection, with each value for i corresponding to a possible outcome of the Projection. The outcome i is witnessed with the probability given by the square norm of the projected state:

$${}_O\langle e_i|\Psi\rangle \in H_S \quad (2)$$

2 The evolution of a physical system does not depend on the Projection step

A crucial insight, previously established in [3], is that the Entanglement step is the only step impacting the physical evolution of the combined system $O + S$. The Projection step, commonly thought to influence subsequent system evolution and measurements, in fact, has no such effect ¹.

To illustrate this, consider a simple scenario: an observer O , a single qubit ² initially in the state $|0\rangle_O$ performs a measurement on a system S , another single qubit initially in the state $|\phi\rangle_S = (|0\rangle_S + |1\rangle_S)/\sqrt{2}$. Suppose that O witnesses the result $|1\rangle_O$. This scenario is depicted in Figure 1, where $|1\rangle_O \langle 1|$ stands for the projection of the Observer's state onto the basis state $|1\rangle_O$.

Figure 1: The observer O measuring S

In this measurement, the Entanglement step is performed by the controlled-NOT gate, which indeed changes the state of the system, from $(|0\rangle_S + |1\rangle_S)/\sqrt{2} \otimes |0\rangle_O$ to $(|0\rangle_S \otimes |0\rangle_S + |1\rangle_S \otimes |1\rangle_O)/\sqrt{2}$. This is a physical evolution which is observable, as it correlates the outcome of subsequent measurements on qubits S and O .

However, the Projection step represented by the projection operator $|1\rangle_O \langle 1|$ does not affect the physical evolution of the system. It is clear that it does not alter the state of the system outside O . The added insight is that the projection does not impact the state for O either, and affects only the outcome of the present measurement. This claim might initially seem in conflict with one implication of quantum mechanics: we should observe $|1\rangle_O$ with certainty if a previous measurement gave $|1\rangle_O$, and that seemingly implies that the first Projection has altered the physical state of the combined system. It is important to note, however, that the measurement in which

¹A related result is that any quantum circuit can be described as a circuit in which no measurement occurs until the very end, as described in [2] and proven later in [4].

²An observer is usually assumed to be a macroscopic system but this does not change the nature of our discussion.

we compare the outcome of the measurement with the result of a previous measurement requires the addition of another system R corresponding to the outcome of the first measurement. The corresponding quantum circuit is shown in Figure 2, which is different from Figure 1.

Figure 2: The observer O measuring S twice, having kept the result of the first outcome

Generally,

- A measurement (1) in which a system is observed in a given state $|a\rangle$ without any further information, and
- A measurement (2) in which this system is observed in $|a\rangle$ together with a record inferring that a previous measurement outcome gave $|a\rangle$

are two distinct measurements with two distinct Projections. The outcome of the measurement (1) is unrelated to the outcome of the measurement (2). What quantum mechanics tells us is that if the measurement (2) is performed, then the outcome of the measurement for the system should be in line with the outcome of the measurement for the record kept from a previous measurement. But we should not forget that verifying consistency with a previous observation is possible only if a physical system acts as a record of the outcome of the previous measurement.

In conclusion, the Projection in a given Measurement has an impact on that specific Measurement only. Namely:

- the choice of the orthonormal basis $\{|e_i\rangle_O\}_i$,
- the outcome of the Projection step,
- the very fact that the Projection step has occurred at all,

impact only what is witnessed in this Projection alone. It has no physical or observable impact outside itself [3] and does not influence any other Projection or any other Measurement. It has no impact on the evolution of the quantum system nor any other measurement performed on the system.

3 A fully unitary description of a quantum circuit

Once we accept the conclusion of the previous section, we can radically simplify our description of a quantum system. To describe the physical evolution of the system, we can remove the Projection steps from all measurements, leaving only the physical interactions necessary for the Entanglement steps which can be represented by unitary gates. The physical evolution is thus purely unitary and deterministic. There is no irreversibility in the evolution of the quantum state of the system, and the knowledge of the state at one instant of time is equivalent to the knowledge of the state at any other time.

So which instant of time should we take as a reference for the specification of the quantum state? We could equally choose this reference time to be at the end of the experiment instead of its beginning, but we could also take a time well before, well after or even in the midst of the experiment. Note however, that if we choose the reference time to be the starting time of the experiment, the quantum state of the system at the beginning is not simply $(|0\rangle_S + |1\rangle_S)/\sqrt{2} \otimes |0\rangle_O$. Indeed, the system $S + O$ could well have been in a completely different state. We happened to have witnessed an experiment which started in the state $(|0\rangle_S + |1\rangle_S)/\sqrt{2} \otimes |0\rangle_O$ but we could have witnessed otherwise. In an experiment, what is measured is not only the outcome of the experiment. The initial state of an experiment is also part of the result of an experiment. In other words, the “initial state” of a quantum circuit should not be considered as an exogenous parameter but as the outcome of an “initial” measurement at the beginning of the experiment. As seen in the previous section, we can remove the Projection part of this initial measurement and obtain a quantum circuit in which we have a unitary and deterministic diffusion of the quantum state throughout the time.

Because the system $S + O$ could interact with other systems before or after the experiment, we need to consider a physical system sufficiently large, call it Ω , to include these ancillary systems. We will call the Environment and denote by E the set of the ancillary system so that $S + O + E = \Omega$. Without loss of generality, we can assume the state of Ω to be a pure state as it is known that any mixed state can be obtained as a partial trace of a pure state in a larger Hilbert space [5]. Because the evolution of Ω is unitary, its state is pure at any time. Let's denote by $|\Psi_{-\infty}\rangle$ the state of Ω at a time $t_{-\infty}$ well before the experiment, and by $|\Psi_{+\infty}\rangle$ the state of Ω at a time $t_{+\infty}$ well after the experiment. For any system X and any times s and t , $U_X(t, s)$ stands for the unitary operator giving the evolution of X between s and t (so that for instance $|\Psi_{+\infty}\rangle = U_\Omega(t_{+\infty}, t_{-\infty})|\Psi_{-\infty}\rangle$). Our first experiment Figure 1 can be represented by the quantum circuit Figure 3, where we assume that $S + O$ is isolated from the environment from a time $t_0 < t_a$ and until a time $t_1 > t_b$.

In this representation, the first set of unspecified number of qubits represents the Environment E . We had supposed that the Environment does

Figure 3: The observer O measuring S in the proposed representation

not interact with S and O during the time interval $[t_0, t_1]$ and undergoes its own unitary evolution $U_E(t_1, t_0)$ during the experiment.

4 Probabilities obtained from the quantum circuit

We have now fully described the unitary evolution corresponding to the experiment, including the entanglement between the observer and the system under study.

To get the joint probability of observing the system $S + O$ in the state $|\phi\rangle_S \otimes |0\rangle_O$ at t_a , and the observer in the state $|1\rangle_O$ at t_b , one only needs to insert the appropriate projections for the corresponding qubits and times, as in Figure 3. This allows us to compute the corresponding probability amplitude directly:

Figure 4: Obtaining the joint probability amplitude for the initial and final states

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_{ab} &= \langle \Psi_{+\infty} | U(t_{+\infty}, t_1) U_E(t_1, t_0) \\
&\quad \otimes [U_{SO}(t_1, t_b) \pi_b U_{SO}(t_b, t_a) \pi_a U_{SO}(t_a, t_0)] \\
&\quad U(t_0, t_{-\infty}) | \Psi_{-\infty} \rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where $\pi_b = \mathbf{1}_S \otimes |1\rangle_O \langle 1|$, $\pi_a = |\phi\rangle_S \langle \phi| \otimes |0\rangle_O \langle 0|$, and with the asymptotic states $|\Psi_{-\infty}\rangle$ and $|\Psi_{+\infty}\rangle$ linked by the relation:

$$\begin{aligned}
|\Psi_{+\infty}\rangle &= U(t_{+\infty}, t_1) U_E(t_1, t_0) \\
&\quad \otimes [U_{SO}(t_1, t_b) U_{SO}(t_b, t_a) U_{SO}(t_a, t_0)] U(t_0, t_{-\infty}) |\Psi_{-\infty}\rangle \\
&= U(t_{+\infty}, t_1) U_E(t_1, t_0) \otimes U_{SO}(t_1, t_0) U(t_0, t_{-\infty}) |\Psi_{-\infty}\rangle \\
&= U(t_{+\infty}, t_{-\infty}) |\Psi_{-\infty}\rangle
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

This process can be generalised for observing the system at multiple times. The probability amplitude of observing the state $|\psi_1\rangle$ at time s_1 , the state $|\psi_2\rangle$ at time s_2 , ..., the state $|\psi_n\rangle$ at time s_n , reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_{1,\dots,n} &= \langle \Psi_{+\infty} | U(t_{+\infty}, t_1) U_E(t_1, t_0) \\
&\quad \otimes [U_{SO}(t_1, s_n) \pi_n U_{SO}(s_n, s_{n-1}) \pi_{n-1} \cdots U_{SO}(s_2, s_1) \pi_1 U_{SO}(s_1, t_0)] \\
&\quad U(t_0, t_{+\infty}) | \Psi_{-\infty} \rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

where $\pi_i = |\psi_i\rangle \langle \psi_i|$ is the projection onto the state $|\psi_i\rangle$.

Coming back to our initial case, the conditional probability of the event b at t_b given that we observe the event a at t_a reads

$$Pr(b|a) = \frac{\chi_{ab}^\dagger \chi_{ab}}{\chi_a^\dagger \chi_a} \tag{6}$$

where χ_a is the probability amplitude of observing $S+O$ in the state $|\phi\rangle_S \otimes |0\rangle_O$ at t_a only, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}
\chi_a &= \langle \Psi_{+\infty} | U(t_{+\infty}, t_1) U_E(t_1, t_0) \\
&\quad \otimes [U_{SO}(t_1, t_a) |\phi\rangle_S \langle \phi| \otimes |0\rangle_O \langle 0| U_{SO}(t_a, t_0)] \\
&\quad U(t_0, t_{+\infty}) | \Psi_{-\infty} \rangle.
\end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

5 Link to the standard formulae

The general formulae above are impractical in most settings as we typically lack a description of the system Ω , its states $|\Psi_{\pm\infty}\rangle$ and its evolution operators U , although we know they obey the relation given in Equation 4.

However, when the system $S + O$ is substantially smaller than the environment E , simplifications to the formulae allow us to approximate them to the conventional expressions of quantum mechanics.

It is known that in such scenarios [6], for almost all pure states for Ω , the state of the subsystem $S + O$ is indistinguishable from the fully mixed state $\frac{1}{d}\mathbf{1}$ where d is the dimension of the Hilbert Space describing $S + O$. We can therefore restrict our analysis of the previous section to the system $S + O$ starting in the fully mixed state $\frac{1}{d}\mathbf{1}$ at t_0 and ending in the fully mixed state $\frac{1}{d}\mathbf{1}$ at t_1 , as any unitary transformation transforms the fully mixed state into the fully mixed state. The joint probability of a and b becomes:

$$Pr(b, a) = \text{Tr} \left(\pi_b U_{SO}(t_b, t_a) \pi_a \left(\frac{1}{d} \mathbf{1} \right) \pi_a U_{SO}^\dagger(t_b, t_a) \pi_b \left(\frac{1}{d} \mathbf{1} \right) \right) \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{1}{d^2} \text{Tr} \left(\pi_b U_{SO}(t_b, t_a) \pi_a U_{SO}^\dagger(t_b, t_a) \right) \quad (9)$$

whereas the marginal probability of observing a is

$$Pr(a) = \frac{1}{d^2} \text{Tr} \left(U_{SO}(t_b, t_a) \pi_a U_{SO}^\dagger(t_b, t_a) \right) \quad (10)$$

$$= \frac{1}{d^2}. \quad (11)$$

From these, the conditional probability of b given a is derived as:

$$Pr(b|a) = \frac{Pr(b, a)}{Pr(a)} = \text{Tr} \left(\pi_b U_{SO}(t_b, t_a) \pi_a U_{SO}^\dagger(t_b, t_a) \right) \quad (12)$$

which is the standard formula giving the conditional probability that we observe b given that the system $S + O$ starts in the state π_a , follows the unitary evolution $U_{SO}(t_b, t_a)$ between t_a and t_b and is measured in state π_b .

6 Time symmetry and absence of causality

What is the interest of our proposal if it gives the same numerical predictions as the standard description of quantum physics? First, note that the equivalence shown in the previous section holds only when the studied physical system is very small compared to the environment, i.e. the rest of the universe [6]. In other words, it may give predictions that are different from the standard formulation when the physical system under consideration is of cosmological scale.

The other advantage of the proposed description is conceptual. Our proposal is based on a clear separation between what is physical evolution and what is subjective observation. We view an experimenter's "initiative" or "choices" as outcomes of measurement rather than as external influences.

This allows to get rid of the notion of causality and preferred flow of time, because we are freed from the labelling of what constitutes a cause and what constitutes a consequence. The resulting formalism offers a clearer symmetry in the role of time and gets rid of the notion of order in physical events.

7 Discussion

Why is causality so persistent in our understanding of quantum systems? Causality is intertwined with notions of initiation, decision, and external intervention – concepts incompatible with closed-system physical laws. Yet, conventional descriptions of quantum evolution frequently imply causality, suggesting a pre-set initial state or an experimenter’s influence on system configuration.

Traditional quantum circuit representations inherit this bias: they start with an initial state on the left, proceed sequentially to the right, and break time symmetry with measurement steps. Our representation, treating past and future equivalently, helps to eliminate these causal implications and the notion of a preferred time direction. Physical laws do not allow any notion of initiative or causal relationships. There are only correlations in observations made conjointly.

This note considered that the quantum circuit itself was deterministic. It could have been otherwise and our formalism does not take into account this possibility. To account for this possibility, we need to consider the whole experimental setup as a configuration of elementary particles that can evolve and to do this we need a quantum field formalism but encompassing the measuring apparatus and the observer, which is far more complex than the current use of quantum field theory.

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